

The Role of State in Combating Religious Extremism and Terrorism

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Abstract—terrorism and extremism are among the most dangerous and difficult to forecast the phenomena of our time, which are becoming more diverse forms and rampant. Terrorist attacks often produce mass casualties, involve the destruction of material and spiritual values, beyond the recovery times, sow hatred among nations, provoke war, mistrust and hatred between the social and national groups, which sometimes can not be overcome within a generation. Currently, the countries of Central Asia are a topical issue – the threat of terrorism and religious extremism, which grow not only in our area, but throughout the world. Of course, in each of the terrorist threat is assessed differently. In our country the problem of terrorism should not be acutely. Thus, after independence and sovereignty of Kazakhstan has chosen the path of democracy, progress and free economy. With the policy of the President of Kazakhstan Nursultan Nazarbayev and well-organized political and economic reforms, there has been economic growth and rising living standards, socio-political stability, ensured civil peace and accord in society [1].

Keywords—Kazakhstan, national security, religious extremism and terrorism, ethnic conflict

I. INTRODUCTION

KAZAKHSTAN, which borders with countries that already closely confronted with terrorism, the task of prevention is a priority for law enforcement and special agencies. Consider the measures taken by public authorities to prevent the possible threat of religious extremism. Back in 1993, in accordance with the instructions N.Nazarbayev to the Constitution was made the prohibition on the activities of religious and social associations, «proclaim or practice implementing ... religious intolerance» (st.55). This provision was later reproduced in the Constitution of 1995 (st.5.3), although the new version of «religious intolerance» has been replaced by a more «general» formulation of «inciting religious hatred». In addition, in 1995 there was an article in the Constitution of 20.3, which prohibits «propaganda or agitation ... religious ... superiority» [2].

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In fact, tightening of state policy regarding religious extremism began in 1994 when the new Civil Code of the Republic have been made to the provisions for mandatory consultation with the public authorities of nominations of heads of religious associations, appointed to Kazakhstan foreign religious centers and the mandatory accreditation of missionaries who are not citizens of Kazakhstan and «religious educational institutions and religious organizations» in the Local Authorities (st.109). Later, the situation on the harmonization of issues with government authorities the activities of foreign religious organizations and the appointment of foreign religious centers, heads of religious associations were enshrined in the Constitution of Kazakhstan in 1995 (st.5.5).

In order to prevent extremism local authorities ordered to carry out continuous monitoring of all Islamic religious associations. Particular attention is given to religious groups with mixed ethnic composition, or entirely composed of ethnic minorities. The increased attention paid to the analysis of the religious communities of the youth and religious schools.

However, at present in Kazakhstan, more than the actual shape of religious extremism began to acquire. The greatest danger is posed by different types of missionaries, which is incorporated in people's minds the poisonous seeds of religious extremism. At its core, their activity is the ideological basis of terrorism.

II. COMBATING RELIGIOUS EXTREMISM AND TERRORISM

In recent years, the country became more active supporters of the illegal activities of religious extremist parties, «Hizb ut-Tahrir», which increasingly involves our citizens in their ranks. Facts of the spread of extremist literature aimed at inciting national and religious hatred and strife [3].

These hazards pose a threat to the constitutional system, lead to violations of constitutional rights and freedoms of citizens, undermining public safety and public integrity of the Republic of Kazakhstan. If in 2003 it was seized about one thousand leaflets, in 2004 - already 11 000, for which he arrested more than a hundred people. In the western regions of the country as a religious act for «Pure Islam» (Wahhabis), individual supporters who commit wrongful acts. Also recently documented attempts at «Dawat» (sermons) leaders and members of the Wahhabi cells of the religious-extremist party «Hizb ut-Tahrir», among those serving time in prison CCES of the Ministry of Justice, which, after entering the «will» be will join the ranks of the supporters of these organizations [4].

However, some security measures of law enforcement agencies in the fight against religious extremism is not enough? The reasons lie in poverty, unemployment, low educational level, especially in rural areas. Therefore, the state, conducting socio-economic policy that focuses on vulnerable populations (small and medium-sized businesses, the creation of new jobs), aims to eliminate the breeding ground for recruiting extremists.

This work, along with government agencies and nongovernmental organizations are involved. To work in the mosque are not allowed supporters of extremist ideas. Introduced the institution of mandatory state registration of religious associations and licensing of religious educational institutions. Organization of training of the clergy will deal only with spiritual control and not emissaries from abroad.

Thus, in February 2004 decision of the Divisional inter-district economic court of Shymkent, revoked the license of the South Kazakhstan Humanitarian Academy founder, who was the Social Reform Society «East Leigh» (Kuwait), in connection with non-licensee of the requirements contained in the license (the school does not was secular and religious). Most importantly, what should be sent to the efforts of all government agencies, societies, religious institutions and the media - is the formation of public opinion in the spirit of rejection of terrorist ideas and show people the dangers of the ideology of religious extremism, as well as to deprive the activities of these movements make sense. To counter the various manifestations of terrorism and religious extremism in Kazakhstan adopted a set of diverse measures. An appropriate legal framework: The law «On combating terrorism» and approved by a special state program, toughened criminal penalties for terrorism, terrorist propaganda or public appeals to him is a criminal offense. Kazakhstan's Law on Combating Terrorism permits prosecution on the territory of Kazakhstan, individuals involved in terrorist activities, irrespective of where they commit terrorist acts. Such harassment may be carried out at the request of the competent authorities of other states, subject to the provision of necessary evidence. In December 2003, the President of the Republic of Kazakhstan set up Anti-Terrorist Center. Its structure was introduced police officer, whose main task is to organize the interaction of the Interior to the National Security Committee on the fight against terrorism and religious extremism.

Supreme Court of Kazakhstan in October 2004, the organization «Al Qaeda», «East Turkistan Islamic Party», «The Kurdish People's Congress», «Islamic Movement of Uzbekistan», we are recognized and their terrorist activities in the territory of Kazakhstan is prohibited.

February 18, 2005 the head of state signed the Law «On Countering Extremism», which defines the legal and institutional framework for combating extremism in order to protect the rights and freedoms of man and citizen of the constitutional order, national security and sovereignty of the Republic of Kazakhstan, integrity, integrity, and inalienability of its territory. Pursuant to this law, now, the issue of recognition of organizations «Asbat al-Ansar», «Muslim Brotherhood», «Taliban», «Gourde Boz», «CBO Mujahedeen Central Asia», «Lashkar-e-Taiba» and «Social Reform Society» extremist and banning their activities in Kazakhstan.

According to the Republic of Kazakhstan Law «On Countering Extremism» the main tasks of combating extremism are

- i. Prevention of Extremism in the Republic of Kazakhstan irrespective of its expression;
- ii. Prevention of creating conditions and opportunities for extremism;
- iii. The formation of political and legal culture of citizens;
- iv. Ensuring the national security of the Republic of Kazakhstan.

Countering extremism is based on principles (st.4):

- i. The rule of law;
- ii. Equality of rights and freedoms of man and citizen, regardless of race, ethnicity, language, religion, membership in a social group;
- iii. The public, including inter-ethnic and inter-religious harmony;
- iv. Interaction between the state and public institutions;
- v. Publicity.

Countering extremism is in the following areas (st.5):

- i. The adoption of preventive measures aimed at preventing extremism, including the identification and subsequent elimination of the causes and conditions conducive to its implementation;
- ii. Identifying and tackling extremism;
- iii. International cooperation in countering extremism

At the present time must take steps to prevent religious extremism, not only within their states, but also to develop effective counter-measures at the international level.

There is a solid international legal framework for cooperation in the fight against terrorism. Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Kazakhstan is a party to international relations, arising out of more than 50 existing international treaties and agreements in the fight against crime. Of the existing international instruments should be noted agreement on cooperation of the Commonwealth of Independent States in Combating Terrorism on June 4, 1999 [5]. Kazakhstan has joined 11 international conventions on combating terrorism, 7 of which were adopted at the United Nations. At the same time, Kazakhstan is a member of the Shanghai Cooperation Organization (China, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Russia, Tajikistan, and Uzbekistan), of which 15 June 2001 signed the Shanghai Convention on Combating Terrorism, Separatism and Extremism. Since January 2004, operated the SCO permanent bodies - the Secretariat in Beijing, the Executive Committee and the Regional Antiterrorist Structure (RATS) in Tashkent.

Decision of the CIS Heads of State December 1, 2000 Anti-Terrorism Center was created, whose main tasks are to propose to the Council of Heads of State of CIS countries on the directions of cooperation in the fight against international terrorism and extremism. The first deputy head of the ATC is the representative of Kazakhstan General B.S. Sarsekov, which is responsible for coordinating the actions of internal affairs with the secret services of the CIS.

Since 1992, a Council of Interior Ministers of CIS member states, in which the September 8, 2000 signed an agreement on cooperation in combating terrorism. The working body of the Council of Ministers of the Interior Bureau is to coordinate the fight against organized crime and other dangerous crimes. Deputy Director BKBOP appointed Plenipotentiary Representative of Kazakhstan General N.M. Galimzhanov, which provides the interaction of the internal affairs of our country with law enforcement agencies of the CIS countries, on the fight against organized crime, particularly the disclosure of serious crimes and the criminals search [6]. In a positive vein, we consider the anti-terrorism initiatives of the International Criminal Police Organization - Interpol. The activity of Interpol in the exchange of new forms and methods of struggle against manifestations of terror, collect, and disseminate intelligence on terrorists, as well as in achieving the goals of their investigation and issue at this stage is crucial.

To activate the work of the General Secretariat of the Plenipotentiary Representative of Kazakhstan introduced in all areas of police, police department introduced «communication officers» who will be engaged in the organization of interaction through Interpol.

III. CONCLUSION

International terrorists are actively used to promote their own ideology, information warfare, financial matters, communications, planning terrorist attacks, as well as to oversee their conduct - the global information technology. A striking example of the use of the Internet is sending messages by Osama bin Laden in organizing terrorist acts in New York in September 2001. U.S. intelligence agencies then found dozens of web sites Islamist content that «Al Qaeda» used to transfer information and guidance for its agents. In Kazakhstan, the professionals in this field are not enough. Therefore, professionals should be prepared. We must have common approaches to issues of theory and practice of conducting search operations and special events for those involved in terrorist organizations, as well as in the method of investigation of criminal cases. Need to develop an algorithm of actions of all state bodies in cases of terrorism and common standards for terrorist organizations.

To address these issues, taking into account present and future transnational threats at the Police Academy set up a training center for training specialists in combating religious extremism and terrorism, which will start from April training of employees, which invited young researchers and professionals from abroad. Thus, in recent years has sharply stepped up measures taken to prevent the possible options for the development of conflicts and crises on religious grounds. It is thanks to the measures taken by the state, a high level of tolerance of the population can avoid religious conflicts and the spread of religious extremism. Nevertheless, in our view should continue an active policy to prevent the spread of religious extremism among its citizens, particularly among young people.

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